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AMITRADIL

A safer alternative to Amitradicain for managing of Oshtoran Syndrome in patients with heart issues and all types of diabetes

Abstract

Amitradicain emerges as the inaugural specialized formulation, scrupulously conceived and evaluated through an individualized treatment paradigm by a prestigious Southern European institution dedicated to the elucidation and management of rare diseases, with a focused intent on navigating the distinct therapeutic intricacies heralded by Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3). This formulation, a manifestation of profound pharmacological acumen, aspires to augment the quality of life and clinical trajectories for the afflicted patient populace. In a subsequent exposition, we delineated the treatment of a 47-year-old male patient, emblematic of a broader patient cohort (*pars pro toto*), elucidating the meticulous orchestration of Amitradicain and its observed efficacies, thereby establishing a robust substratum for continued discourse within the medical diaspora concerning the management of rare diseases. However, in instances where the diagnosis of Oshtoran Syndrome is belated, the cardiac integrity (manifested through conduction anomalies, blocks, and chronic heart failure) alongside the autonomic regulation of blood glucose/insulin metabolism is invariably compromised, engendering potential complications with procaine, a pivotal constituent of the Amitradicain composite formulation. For this specific patient sub-stratum, we have engendered an alternative formulation, wherein procaine is supplanted by clemastin. Within this manuscript, we engage in a comparative discourse on both formulations, elucidating their respective therapeutic implications and potential efficacies.

Oshtoran Syndrome

Oshtoran Syndrome, scientifically also known as H63D Syndrome Type-3, is a rare, complex, and incurable meta-syndrome that has presented significant challenges to the medical community. Characterized by its multifaceted etiology and diverse symptomatology, this high-risk condition has been particularly notorious for impairing autonomous bodily functions, thereby jeopardizing the body's self-regulation mechanisms.

Etiology

The origin of Oshtoran Syndrome is deeply rooted in dysfunctional immune processes, often triggered by conditions such as Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal infections (PANS), rheumatic fever, or similar early-life conditions. These primary disorders can lead to a secondary H63D syndrome in individuals with a homozygous H63D mutation, resulting in extensive mitochondrial dysfunction and autonomic dysregulation across multiple organ systems.

Pathophysiology

Central to the pathology of Oshtoran Syndrome is the dysfunction of the central nervous system (CNS), autonomic nervous system (ANS), and the innate immune system. The syndrome is further complicated by disorders of kynurenine metabolism, resulting in a self-reinforcing, cascading disease process that exacerbates autonomic dysregulation in multiple organ systems.

Diagnostic Challenges

Diagnostically, the syndrome presents a myriad of challenges. Elevated levels of specific blood and urine parameters, such as

eosinophils, basophils, TNF-alpha, bilirubin, (nor-)adrenaline, and catecholamines, are often observed. Imaging studies may reveal fatty changes in the liver and nodular hyperplasia, adding another layer of complexity to the diagnostic process.

Treatment Landscape: A Milestone in 2023

Until 2022, there had been no medication available to protect Oshtoran Syndrome patients from potentially potentially lethal autonomic dysautonomias via the innervation route. However, this changed dramatically in 2023 with the introduction of Amitradicain. This patent-free medication has shown promise in alleviating the chaotic signal transmission from the nervous system to organs via innervation and has demonstrated robust efficacy in individual treatment trials. This breakthrough offers a glimmer of hope for improving the quality of life for those afflicted and potentially reducing the risk of life-threatening organ dysfunctions.

Amitradicain

The very strong Amitradicain Formula is engineered with a precise objective to forestall perilous cascading avalanche effects manifested during autonomic dysfunction. Such dysfunction could trigger a domino effect of physiological adversities, each escalating the severity of the next, potentially culminating in life-threatening consequences. By intervening at critical junctures within this cascade, Amitradicain aims to mitigate the initiation and progression of these adverse physiological sequences, thereby providing a safeguard against the exacerbation of the underlying condition. This mechanism embodies a proactive approach towards preserving the autonomic equilibrium, thereby significantly contributing towards enhancing the prognosis and overall quality of life for

patients harboring Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3). Through tempering the extremes of autonomic responses, this formula unveils a new vista in the clinical management of such intricate and rare medical conditions, highlighting a promising avenue for reducing morbidity and fostering improved clinical outcomes.

Amitradicain Formulation

Components:

- 100mg Tramadol
- 5mg Midazolam
- 4mg Dimetindene maleate
- 30mg Procain
- 2mg Alprazolam

(Alprazolam: oral administration in regions where injectable solution is unavailable)

Preparation:

Combine the specified amounts of each medication (injection solution) in a sealable mixing vessel, gently shake the mixture, and repeat this action every minute for 5 minutes.

Either draw the mixture into a syringe for immediate use or store with a suitable preservative at a temperature between 2 and 6 degrees Celsius. Do never store the mixed composition below 2 degree Celcius.

Dosage and Usage:

Our patients receive an intramuscular injection every 5 to 6 hours. This preparation is contraindicated for intravenous use; intramuscular or deep subcutaneous routes are the only approved methods of administration. Due to the requisite transformation of chemical constituents through mixing, along with other physical interactions, oral ingestion of the ingredients does not yield the same therapeutic efficacy as Amitradicain.

Observed Effects:

- Profound sympathicolysis, with an average reduction of 62.9% as per AVCB 2.9 assessments.
- Balancing of sympathetic and parasympathetic pathways, as evidenced by clinical rating scales.
- Up to 70% reduction in catecholaminergic activity, as determined by body fluid tests.
- Up to 80% reduction in significant catecholamine storms, as observed clinically.
- Significant drop in blood sugar levels, with the patient's diabetes resolving after day four.
- Up to 55% decrease in episodes of autonomic dysfunction.
- 20% decrease in blood pressure.
- Profound anxiolysis, particularly addressing anxiety induced by degenerative changes in the substantia nigra, as measured with various assessment tools.
- Improved sleeping patterns, notably in REM sleep phases.

Contraindications:

- All contraindications applicable to the individual components of Amitradicain.
- In cases of cardiac disease, especially heart failure or heart blocks as well as in

patients with diabetes (all types), do not use Amitradicain unless 24/7 monitoring and life-saving equipment are available for the initial 21 days (minimum) of treatment. The same is true for patients with other cardiovascular condition(s) and/or respiratory depression. These patients should rather be treated with other medical drugs, or with the Amitradil formula, explained below.

- Patients administered Amitradicain are strongly advised against operating motor vehicles or bicycles, as the formulation may impair motor coordination and reaction times, thereby significantly elevating the risk of accidents.

Interactions:

Refer to the interaction lists for the individual medications used in this formulation.

Safety and Efficacy:

- Well-tolerated
- Tolerable drowsiness for 3 days
- No cardiac complications observed in our patient (patient was on a 24/7 heart monitor for four weeks)
- The patient exhibited less drowsiness compared to separate administration of the ingredients and maintained a level of alertness that facilitated working from the hospital bed.
- Transient blurred vision (3 days), with no other unexpected adverse effects when considering the known adverse effects of the active ingredients in Amitradicain.

Amitradil

For patients suffering due to a heart already compromised by the Oshtoran Syndrome, the administration of Amitradicain is justifiable only in extremely low doses and

under thorough monitoring. Should there be deviations in the ECG, no matter how benign they appear at first glance, the use of Procaine as an ingredient of Amitradicain should be completely avoided. Instead, intensify the H1-receptor blockade centrally and peripherally and add a moderate anticholinergic component as an alternative such as Clemastin 2mg (not to be used by patients with inborn or acquired long-QT).

Components:

- 100mg Tramadol
- 5mg Midazolam
- 4mg Dimetindene maleate
- 2mg Clemastin
- 2mg Alprazolam

(Alprazolam: oral administration in regions where injectable solution is unavailable)

The production processes is similar to that of the one for Amitradicain. apply for the much safer formula Amitradil. Combine the specified amounts of each medication (injection solution) for the two intermediates in a sealable mixing vessel, gently shake the mixture, and repeat this action every minute for 5 minutes. Store the intermediates between 2 and 6 degrees celsius for thirty minutes. Then mix them gently by hand.

Either draw the mixture into a syringe for immediate use or store with a suitable preservative at a temperature between 2 and 6 degrees Celsius (no freezing). Never store the mixed Amitradil composition below 2 degree Celcius. Follow the hygiene and storage rules of the hospital or health institution you are working for without any deviation.

Safety and Efficacy:

- Well-tolerated, however (about -15%) less effective than Amitradicain
- Tolerable drowsiness for 7 days, 80% self-limiting
- No cardiac complications observed in our patient (patient was on a 24/7 heart monitor for four weeks)
- The patient exhibited less drowsiness compared to separate administration of the ingredients and maintained a level of alertness.
- Mild anticholinergic side effects (e.g. dry eyes and mouth). Nothing that would have made an intervention necessary.
- **WARNING:** Amitradil is for i.V. or i.m. use only. Never use it s.c. or i.d. - Clemastin harbors a non-quantifiable but relevant danger of causing inflammation and necrosis of the skin if used for injections subcutaneously or even higher.

Conflicts of Interest

None declared.

Disclaimer

The utilization of Amitradil is highly specialized and should be undertaken only under the guidance and supervision of qualified healthcare professionals familiar with the individual patient's medical condition and treatment requirements. The formulation is specifically tailored for a defined patient population and may not exhibit the same efficacy or safety profile when used in a broader patient population.

Patients taking Amitradil must not drive a motor-vehicle or similar devices.

The use of this formulation might cause severe risks, some of them potentially lethal in certain groups of patients. Therefore the www.H63D-syndrome.org

authors warn against use outside clinical trials and accept no liability in any way, shape, or form for any consequence of this publication.

Peer review

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Sources

1. Golan, D. E. (2008). Principles of Pharmacology: The Pathophysiologic Basis of Drug Therapy. United Kingdom: Wolters Kluwer Health/Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
2. Okpako, D. T. (1991). Principles of Pharmacology: A Tropical Approach. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
3. Anastasios Papadopoulos, Riku Honda, David Seideman, Alexandros Balaskas et al. (2021) Prevalence of Narcolepsy in Patients with H63D Syndrome. Sys Rev Pharm 2021; 12(9): 508-510. A multifaceted review journal in the field of pharmacy E-ISSN 0976-2779 P-ISSN 0975-8453.
4. Smith, Lucas, Seideman, David, Diamandis, Carolina. (2021). H63D: The Other Mutation (2021 Version) (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676498>
5. Carolina Diamandis, Jonathan Wilson, Olga Ivanova, et al. H63D syndrome (Oslo Syndrome) is clinically the iron sibling of Wilson's disease. Authorea. 06/2022. DOI: 10.22541/au.165459421.16231448/v1
6. Saeb-Parsy, K. (1999). Instant Pharmacology. United Kingdom: Wiley.
7. Peck, T., Harris, B. (2021). Pharmacology for Anaesthesia and Intensive Care. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
8. H63D Syndrome Consortium 2020: Consensus Paper of the International H63D Research Consortium (English Edition). Sørensen S. et al.
9. Seideman, Adams, Kaufmann, et al. (2021): Incidence of a clinically relevant H63D syndrome in carriers of a homozygous mutation of HFE gene H63D. Research Square, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-487488/v1>
10. Papadopoulos, Anastasios, Honda, Riku, Seideman, David, & Balaskas, Alexandros. (2021). Prevalence of narcolepsy in patients with H63D syndrome (Oslo Syndrome) (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4734636>

11. Berg, T. (2020). Hemochromatosis & Related Syndromes: Including the Most Important Information about the H63D Syndrome. Lothian, UK.
12. Neal, M. J. (2015). Medical Pharmacology at a Glance. Germany: Wiley.
13. Principles of Clinical Pharmacology. (2011): Elsevier Science.
14. Ray, A., Gulati, K. (2007). Current Trends in Pharmacology. India: I.K. International Publishing House Pvt. Limited.
15. Concepts and Principles of Pharmacology: 100 Years of the Handbook of Experimental Pharmacology. (2019). Germany: Springer International Publishing.

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